

1 **Microwave-assisted ternary deep eutectic solvent pretreatment for**
2 **improved rice straw saccharification under mild pretreatment conditions**

3 Helena Poy, Estela Lladosa*, Adrián Arcís, Carmen Gabaldón, Sonia Loras

4 Department of Chemical Engineering, Universitat de València, Av. De la Universitat

5 S/N, 46100, Burjassot, Spain.

6

*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: estela.lladosa@uv.es (E. Lladosa)

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8 **ABSTRACT**

9 The development of a green and cost-effective pretreatment method to overcome
10 biomass recalcitrance is a challenging assignment for the efficient valorization of
11 lignocellulosic compounds. In this study, a ternary deep eutectic solvent (DES) consisting
12 of choline chloride (ChCl), p-toluene sulfonic acid (pTSA) and ethylene glycol (EG) was
13 applied in rice straw (RS) pretreatment under microwave (MW) irradiation for the further
14 conversion of the polysaccharide fraction. The effect of the pretreatment temperature, time
15 and pTSA content in the DES on lignin extraction and polysaccharide hydrolysis was
16 assessed by a central composite design (CCD). Under the selected pretreatment conditions
17 (80 °C, 22.5 min, ChCl:pTSA:EG 1:1:9), 61.6% delignification was achieved, as well as
18 nearly complete conversion of the initial glucan in RS (93.4% glucose yield) and a good
19 xylan conversion rate (48.3% xylose yield), representing a total polysaccharide
20 exploitation of 78.3%. Energetical requirement was remarkably lower compared to
21 conventional conductive heating. Importantly, the ternary DES showed good recyclability
22 pattern after two reuses. Overall, this study demonstrated the potential of MW-assisted
23 ternary DES pretreatment for improved valorization of biomass polysaccharides under
24 mild pretreatment conditions, representing an efficient and energetical-saving alternative
25 pathway within the biorefinery framework.

26 **Keywords**

27 Ternary deep eutectic solvent; Pretreatment; Rice straw; Microwave irradiation;
28 Saccharification

29 **Abbreviations***

30

* CCD, central composite design; **CH**, **conductive heating**; ChCl, choline chloride; **CrI**, **crystallinity index**; DES, deep eutectic solvent; EG, ethylene glycol; HBA, hydrogen bond acceptor; HBD, hydrogen bond donor; MW, microwave; pTSA, p-toluenesulfonic acid; RS, rice straw; RSM, response surface method.

31 **1. Introduction**

32 Due to the gradual exhaustion of fossil fuel reserves and the ever-increasing
33 environmental issues, the valorization of lignocellulosic biomass as a renewable, low-cost
34 and carbon-neutral feedstock has been widely considered to mitigate society's reliance on
35 conventional petrochemical resources (Chourasia et al., 2022). Among lignocellulosic
36 sources, rice straw (RS) is one of the most abundant wastes worldwide with a high
37 potential for biochemical conversion within the biorefinery framework, owing to its
38 predominant polysaccharide fraction composed of cellulose (32-47% w/w) and
39 hemicellulose (10-27% w/w) along with a relatively low lignin content (3-24% w/w)
40 compared to other biomass species such as wheat straw (Karimi et al., 2006). As a
41 lignocellulosic source, the complex linkages between carbohydrates and lignin results in a
42 rigid and recalcitrant structure, causing a bottleneck in the release of fermentable sugars
43 from RS for the production of biofuels or value-added chemicals (Song et al., 2019).
44 Pretreatment is thus a crucial step in the efficient conversion of biomass, which involves
45 breaking down the recalcitrant structure of lignocellulose, removing lignin and enhancing
46 the accessibility to polysaccharides.

47 Biomass pretreatment can make up 40-60% of the total costs, underscoring the
48 critical need for the development of environmentally friendly and cost-effective
49 pretreatment methods towards the establishment of a sustainable and economically viable
50 biorefinery process (Xu et al., 2023). Recently, deep eutectic solvents (DES) have become
51 a research hotspot in the field of lignocellulose pretreatment owing to their high selectivity
52 for extracting lignin rather than cellulose, which enables the sustainable valorization of the
53 isolated lignin and residual cellulose (Francisco et al., 2012). DES are mixtures formed by
54 a hydrogen bond acceptor (HBA) and a hydrogen bond donor (HBD), presenting a lower
55 melting point than that of the individual components. The remarkable features of DES,

56 including easy preparation, tunability, recyclability, low toxicity and volatility, and
57 biodegradability make them highly suitable for use in biorefineries (Sharma et al., 2022).

58 The DES commonly used in biomass pretreatment consist of binary mixtures of
59 choline chloride (ChCl) as HBA combined with carboxylic acids or polyalcohols as HBD.
60 While carboxylic acids show higher efficiency in the pretreatment step due to the presence
61 of more active protons for the attack, polyalcohol-based DES exhibit excellent
62 recyclability as well as compatibility with enzymes and microorganisms (Hong et al.,
63 2020). Nevertheless, the use of carboxylic acids as HBD in biomass pretreatment have
64 shown certain limitations such as esterification reactions in both the DES itself (Rodriguez
65 Rodriguez et al., 2019) and between the DES and the lignocellulosic compounds (Morais
66 et al., 2021). In contrast, using aromatic acids such as p-toluenesulfonic acid (pTSA) or
67 benzenesulfonic acid as acidic HBD can circumvent this concern, as their esterification
68 tendency has been demonstrated to be minimal (<1% esterification yield) (Teasdale et al.,
69 2010).

70 Recent studies have shown the benefits of using ternary DES composed of an
71 intrinsic acid and a polyalcohol as HBDs. These systems provide the required protons and
72 active sites for the disruption of the recalcitrant lignocellulosic matrix while avoiding the
73 condensation reactions and degradation concerns associated with the use of binary acidic
74 DES (Yu et al., 2022). For instance, the addition of ethylene glycol (EG) to the binary
75 mixture ChCl:Oxalic acid reduced the condensation of extracted lignin from birchwood
76 from 53% to 15%, which improved the glucose saccharification yield from 58.8% to
77 95.9% (Liu et al., 2021). Regarding an intrinsic acid, pTSA as a strong acid ($pK_a = -2.8$)
78 could be a good HBD candidate due to its excellent ability to donate protons to solvents
79 and its lower energy requirements for extracting lignin (70-80 °C, 1-8 h) than carboxylic
80 acid-DES (120 °C, ~6 h) lignocellulosic attack than carboxylic acid-DES

81 (Balasubramanian and Venkatachalam, 2023; da Costa Lopes et al., 2020), so that
82 incorporating it in a ternary DES would help to reduce the severity of the pretreatment.

83 Despite the significant advances reported in DES pretreatment, the long times and
84 high temperatures required (up to 175 °C and 24 h) (Tan et al., 2020) remain a major
85 challenge in terms of energy efficiency. Integrating microwave (MW) irradiation has
86 proved to improve DES pretreatment due to the fast and uniform heating at molecular
87 level, which contributes in reducing the pretreatment time from hours to minutes
88 (Chourasia et al., 2022). Additionally, MW irradiation can maximize DES's ionic
89 character, which increases their molecular polarity and in turn enables the use of lower
90 temperatures and times without compromising pretreatment efficiency (Tan et al., 2020).
91 In this regard, previous studies have shown that MW-assisted DES pretreatment offers
92 higher enzymatic conversion rates while requiring a significantly lower energy
93 consumption compared to conductive heating methods (Kumar et al., 2019).

94 In this context, the present work evaluated the effectiveness of MW-assisted ternary
95 DES under mild pretreatment conditions for the further enzymatic conversion of both main
96 sugars from RS, glucan and xylan, aiming at maximizing its preservation in the
97 pretreatment step for an improved valorization of RS. For this purpose, a ternary DES
98 consisting of ChCl as HBA, pTSA as acidic HBD and ethylene glycol (EG) as diol HBD
99 was used. To gain a comprehensive knowledge on the behavior of MW-DES over the
100 disruption of RS, a central composite design (CCD) based on the response surface method
101 (RSM) was employed, studying the effect of three pretreatment variables (temperature,
102 time, and pTSA mole content) on delignification, as well as in the hydrolysis of glucose
103 and xylose. Overall, this research provides comprehensive insights into a novel, efficient,
104 and energy-efficient pretreatment method designed to enhance the conversion of RS into
105 fermentable sugars. These findings hold the potential to bring about new perspectives for

106 optimizing biomass processing, moving towards simpler, quicker, and more energy-
107 efficient pretreatment processes to promote sustainability within the biorefinery
108 framework.

109 **2. Materials and methods**

110 *2.1 Materials*

111 Rice straw (RS) was provided by local producers from the Albufera Natural Park
112 (Valencia, Spain). Before use, the raw feedstock was ground and sieved to attain a particle
113 size range between 100 and 500 μm . For the synthesis of DES, choline chloride (ChCl,
114 99% w/w) from VWR Chemicals (Radnor, PA, USA), p-toluenesulfonic acid monohydrate
115 (pTSA, >98% w/w) from TCI chemicals (Zwijndrecht, Belgium) and ethylene glycol (EG,
116 >99.8%w/w) from Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA) were used. All the chemicals
117 were used without further purification. The cellulase cocktail (Cellic CTec2) used for
118 saccharification assays was acquired from Novozymes (Bagsværd, Denmark).

119 *2.2 Synthesis of DES*

120 Ternary DES synthesis was carried out by mixing ChCl as hydrogen bond acceptor
121 (HBA) with pTSA and EG as hydrogen bond donors (HBDs) at different molar ratios. The
122 mixtures ChCl:pTSA:EG (1:0-2:9) were heated at 60 °C and magnetically stirred until
123 transparent homogeneous solvents were formed and then allowed to stirred for 1 h at room
124 temperature prior to storing under ambient conditions. Five different DES mixtures were
125 prepared based on the statistical design described in section 2.6.

126 *2.3 Microwave-assisted DES pretreatment of RS*

127 The pretreatment process was performed in a Multiwave GO microwave (MW)
128 reactor (1000 W maximum power, Anton Paar GmbH, Austria) at a 10% (w/w) biomass
129 loading. The samples were heated from room temperature to the specified temperature (50-
130 110 °C) at a rate of 11°C/min. Once the desired temperature was reached, the extraction

131 time was held to 5-40 min and then compressed air was applied to cool the sample down to
132 50 °C. Afterwards, 50% (w/w) ethanol/water (x3 w/w respect to DES) was added to the
133 slurry and the phases were separated by centrifugation, with five successive washings. The
134 pretreated RS was recovered by vacuum filtration and dried in a ventilated oven at 40 °C
135 for 24 h and finally stored at 4 °C until analysis and saccharification. The solid recovery
136 was calculated as the percentage of solid obtained after pretreatment based on the initial
137 sample (dry weight).

138 For the selected pretreatment conditions, a preliminary study to assess the
139 feasibility of the DES reuse was carried out. After pretreatment, the mixture ethanol/water
140 was separated by vacuum distillation in a rotary evaporator (50 °C). Subsequently, water
141 was added (x3 w/w respect to DES) as antisolvent, and the mixture was kept overnight at 4
142 °C. After separating the precipitated solids by centrifugation (6000 rpm, 5 min), water was
143 removed in a rotary evaporator and DES was reused in the next cycle without further
144 purification.

145 *2.4 Conductive heating of RS with DES*

146 RS was pretreated under conductive heating (CH) using a reciprocating shaker
147 (2300 W at 250 °C, rotaterm, Selecta, Barcelona, Spain) and a 10% w/w of solid loading.
148 Pretreatment was carried out at 80 °C for 22.5 and 45 min under an agitation rate of 100
149 rpm. Afterwards, sample was processed according to section 2.3.

150 *2.5 Biomass characterization*

151 The structural carbohydrate and lignin content in untreated and pretreated RS were
152 analyzed by two-step acid hydrolysis, according to the standard procedure reported by the
153 National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) (Sluiter et al., 2012). Acid insoluble
154 lignin (AIL) was gravimetrically determined after drying and a calcination, while acid
155 soluble lignin (ASL) was determined by measuring the absorbance of the hydrolysate at

156 320 nm. Glucan and xylan content were obtained by correcting the monomeric sugar
157 concentration with the corresponding anhydrous factor (0.90 for glucose and 0.88 for
158 xylose). Monomeric sugars were analyzed by high performance liquid chromatography
159 (HPLC) (Agilent HPLC 1100 Series, Agilent Technologies, USA) equipped with a
160 refractive index detector (RID) and an Aminex HPX-87H column (300 mm × 7.8 mm, Bio-
161 Rad Laboratories Inc., USA). The column was operated at 50 °C and 0.6 mL/min of 5 mM
162 H₂SO₄ as the mobile phase. Pretreatment efficiency was assessed from the following
163 criteria:

$$Delignification (\%) = 100 - \frac{Lignin\ in\ pretreated\ RS(\%) \cdot Solid\ recovery\ (\%)}{Lignin\ in\ untreated\ RS\ (\%)} \quad (1)$$

$$Sugar\ recovery\ (\%) = \frac{Sugar\ in\ pretreated\ RS\ (\%) \cdot Solid\ recovery\ (\%)}{Sugar\ in\ untreated\ RS\ (\%)} \quad (2)$$

164 The relative crystallinity of untreated and some pretreated samples was analyzed by
165 X-ray powder diffractometry (XRD) using a Bruker D8 Advance A25 X-ray
166 Diffractometer (Bruker, USA) equipped with Cu radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). Samples were
167 measured in the range of 5-50 ° with a step size of 0.02° and step time of 1 s. The
168 crystallinity index (CrI) of the samples was obtained according to the Segal method (Segal
169 et al., 1959).

170 2.6 Saccharification assays

171 Enzymatic hydrolysis of untreated and pretreated RS samples was performed with
172 8% (w/v) of the substrate in 50 mM sodium acetate buffer (pH 5.5) according to a previous
173 study (Poy et al., 2023). Saccharification reactions were conducted in a shaking incubator
174 at 50 °C for 72 h with a cellulase dosage of 30 FPU/g biomass of Cellic CTec2. The
175 released glucose and xylose were analyzed by HPLC as described above and the joint
176 efficiency of pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis, expressed as glucose and xylose
177 yield, was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Sugar yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Sugar hydrolyzed (g/L)} \cdot \text{Solid recovery (\%)}}{\text{Biomass loading (g/L)} \cdot \text{Sugar in untreated RS (\%)}} \quad (3)$$

178 2.7 Design of experiments and statistical analysis

179 CCD based on RSM was employed to assess the effect of three pretreatment
 180 variables (temperature, time and pTSA mole content) on the removal of lignin, as well as
 181 glucose and xylose saccharification. Each variable was examined at five levels (- α , -1, 0,
 182 +1, + α) as shown in Table 1, resulting in an experimental design of twenty test with six
 183 replicates of the central point. The experimental data were analyzed on R® 4.2.1 software
 184 and fitted into a quadratic polynomial model in the following form:

$$y (\%) = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i x_i + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{ii} x_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j \neq i}^n \beta_{ij} x_i x_j \quad (4)$$

185 Where y represents the predicted response (delignification, glucose yield or xylose
 186 yield), x_i, x_j the independent variables and $\beta_0, \beta_i, \beta_{ii}$ and β_{ij} represent the constant, linear,
 187 quadratic and interaction coefficients of the model, respectively. The models' significance
 188 and adequacy, plus effects of significant individual terms and their various interactions on
 189 the different responses were evaluated by analysis of variance (ANOVA). The CCD was
 190 statically analyzed at a 95% confidence interval ($p = 0.05$). Three-dimensional plots were
 191 generated to illustrate the effects of the pretreatment variables on the responses analyzed
 192 (delignification, glucose yield and xylose yield).

193 **Table 1.** Levels of the pretreatment conditions variables tested in the CCD.

Process variables		Levels				
		- α	-1	0	+1	+ α
A	Temperature, °C	50.0	62.2	80.0	97.8	110.0
B	time, min	5.0	12.1	22.5	32.9	40.0
C	pTSA, mole content ^a	0.0	0.4	1.0	1.6	2.0

^aIn the mixture ChCl:pTSA:EG

194 **3. Results and discussion**

195 *3.1 Effect of MW-assisted DES pretreatment on RS dissolution and chemical composition*

196 In this study, MW-assisted DES pretreatment was used as a prior step to valorize
 197 the sugars contained in RS through enzymatic hydrolysis. Therefore, the selective
 198 extraction of lignin without compromising the sugar content plays a key role in efficient
 199 exploitation of the potential monosaccharide content contained in the raw material. Table 2
 200 summarizes the main effects of MW-assisted DES pretreatment on RS fractionation,
 201 including the solid recovery, the main chemical composition of untreated and pretreated
 202 solids, the recovery of polysaccharides and the degree of delignification.

203 **Table 2.** CCD experimental matrix and data of compositional analysis, sugar recovery and
 204 delignification obtained after MW-assisted DES pretreatment.

Run	Pretreatment conditions ^a			Solid recovery (%)	Main composition (% w/w)			Sugar recovery/Delignification (%)		
	A	B	C		Glucan	Xylan	Lignin	Glucan recovery	Xylan recovery	Delignification
Raw RS					35.6	17.6	11.4	-		
1	62.2	12.1	0.4	89.0	39.6	18.3	11.1	99.0	92.3	13.6
2 ^b	80.0	22.5	1.0	71.8	48.1	16.3	7.1	96.9	66.2	55.3
3 ^b	80.0	22.5	1.0	66.1	48.9	15.6	6.1	90.8	58.4	64.6
4	50.0	22.5	1.0	84.6	41.1	18.7	11.4	97.7	90.0	15.7
5	97.8	12.1	0.4	67.6	51.6	14.8	9.5	98.0	56.9	43.7
6	110.0	22.5	1.0	57.9	53.9	11.2	9.2	87.7	36.9	53.2
7	62.2	32.9	1.6	75.0	46.3	17.5	9.7	97.4	74.6	36.6
8 ^b	80.0	22.5	1.0	69.2	49.0	16.1	6.7	95.1	63.4	59.6
9 ^b	80.0	22.5	1.0	70.1	49.1	16.1	7.1	96.6	64.1	56.6
10 ^b	80.0	22.5	1.0	64.6	54.2	15.1	5.8	98.3	55.3	67.4
11	97.8	32.9	0.4	62.0	53.6	13.1	8.4	93.2	46.2	54.2
12	80.0	22.5	2.0	62.8	53.0	13.8	5.8	93.4	49.2	68.1
13	97.8	32.9	1.6	57.9	58.4	11.1	5.5	95.1	36.6	72.0
14	97.8	12.1	1.6	60.8	57.2	12.5	6.4	97.6	43.0	65.8
15	80.0	40.0	1.0	64.5	51.0	14.2	7.1	92.4	52.0	59.7
16 ^b	80.0	22.5	1.0	66.0	51.1	15.3	5.9	94.8	57.4	66.1
17	80.0	22.5	0.0	90.7	38.0	18.1	10.8	96.9	93.2	14.6
18	62.2	12.1	1.6	83.4	42.2	19.0	10.7	98.9	90.1	22.0
19	80.0	5.0	1.0	78.4	44.0	18.6	11.4	96.9	82.8	21.8
20	62.2	32.9	0.4	85.0	41.1	18.3	10.7	98.2	88.6	20.0

^a A: Temperature (°C); B: time (min); C: pTSA (mole content).

^b Central point of the experimental design.

205

206 The percentage of solid recovered after pretreatment ranged from 57.9% to 90.7%,
207 and generally declined as the severity of the pretreatment increased, indicating that higher
208 temperatures, longer times and higher pTSA content in the DES favored the dissolution of
209 RS under MW irradiation. The acidity of the DES, governed by the pTSA content in the
210 ternary mixture, seems to play a major role in the dissolution of RS. Notably, the minimum
211 RS dissolution occurred when pTSA was absent in the DES (run 17), obtaining the highest
212 solid recovery of all the conditions tested (90.7% solid recovery), which declined
213 remarkably to a mean value of 68% by only increasing the pTSA mole content to 1.0
214 (central points).

215 For all pretreatment conditions tested, the glucan content in pretreated samples was
216 boosted to 38.0-58.4% compared to the initial content in the raw material (35.6% glucan;
217 Table 2) which was attributed to the extraction of other non-cellulosic compounds. As can
218 be seen in Table 2, glucan was well preserved in all scenarios (87.7-99.0 % glucan
219 recovery), confirming that cellulose was not significantly hydrolyzed or degraded after
220 MW-assisted DES pretreatment. According to previous studies, the strong cohesive energy
221 of cellulose was found to hamper the dissociation and reorganization of the hydrogen-
222 bonding networks necessary for the successful dissolution of cellulose in DES (Vigier et
223 al., 2015). Furthermore, it has also been reported that ChCl is able to stabilize the DES-
224 cellulose system by forming a strong hydrogen bonding network, which in turns hinders
225 cellulose dissolution (Mankar et al., 2021). However, it should be noted that further
226 increasing the pretreatment temperature could promote degradation of the cellulose, as
227 found when it was raised from 80 °C (95.4% glucan recovery; central point average) to 110
228 °C (87.7% glucan recovery; run 6).

229 Regarding to the lignin fraction, its content in pretreated solids was reduced (5.5-
230 11.4% lignin content) to a value below the untreated biomass (11.4% lignin), confirming

231 the selective extraction of lignin over cellulose in the pretreatment step. Unlike glucan,
232 MW-assisted DES pretreatment could not maintain the secondary source of sugars in RS as
233 efficiently as in the case of cellulose due to its sensitivity under acidic conditions,
234 achieving xylan recoveries from 36.6% to 93.2% (Table 2). Further analyzing the results, a
235 strong linear relationship was found between xylan recovery and delignification ($R^2 =$
236 0.89; Fig. S1), indicating that xylan and lignin were simultaneously extracted during the
237 MW-assisted DES pretreatment. This finding confirmed that the MW-assisted DES
238 pretreatment displayed the same biomass dissolution mechanism as conventional acidic
239 DES pretreatment, which is governed by the proton-catalyzed cleavage of ether bonds in
240 lignin, glycosidic bonds in polysaccharides, as well as ether/ester bonds between lignin and
241 hemicellulose, leading the joint extraction of hemicellulose and lignin over cellulose
242 (Wang and Lee, 2021). The pretreatment conditions should thus be monitored to control
243 the severity of the pretreatment and avoid sugar extraction or degradation, while providing
244 efficient delignification to enhance the enzymatic accessibility to polysaccharides.

245 3.2 Effect of MW-assisted DES pretreatment on RS delignification: statistical analysis

246 Owing to the importance of pretreatment in fractionating lignin from biomass,
247 delignification was evaluated through a CCD to study the influence of the selected
248 pretreatment variables (temperature, time and pTSA content) with the minimum number of
249 experiments. As can be seen in Table 2, the delignification obtained after MW-assisted
250 DES pretreatment varied from 13.6% (run 1) to 72.0% (run 13), showing wide variability
251 according to the pretreatment conditions used. After fitting the experimental data by
252 multiple regression analysis, the following second-degree polynomial model was obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Delignification (\%)} = & -258.30 + 5.19 \cdot \text{Temperature} + 3.62 \cdot \text{time} + 39.68 \cdot \text{pTSA} - \\ & 2.78\text{E}^{-2} \cdot \text{Temperature}^2 - 6.13\text{E}^{-2} \cdot \text{time}^2 - 18.16 \text{pTSA}^2 - 2.89\text{E}^{-3} \cdot \text{Temperature} \cdot \text{time} + \\ & 0.17 \cdot \text{Temperature} \cdot \text{pTSA} + 7.91\text{E}^{-2} \cdot \text{time} \cdot \text{pTSA} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

253 The main results of the ANOVA and the coded regression coefficients of the above
 254 quadratic model are shown in Table 3. The statistical analysis showed that the model was
 255 highly significant at a 95% confidence level ($p = 0.0003$), while the lack of fit was not ($p =$
 256 0.0691), indicating the suitability and strength of the fitted model. At the same time, the
 257 high values of the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.9177$) and the adjusted coefficient
 258 of determination (adj. $R^2 = 0.8435$) confirmed that the model accurately fitted the
 259 experimental data and could predict the effect of the pretreatment temperature, time and
 260 pTSA content on the extraction of lignin from RS.

261 **Table 3.** ANOVA results of the CCD model for delignification as response.

Source	Sum of squares	df ^a	Mean square	F-value	p-value	Coefficient ^b
Model	7650.54	9	850.06	12.38	0.0003	61.50
A–Temperature	3126.79	1	3126.79	45.55	0.0001	15.13
B–time	752.98	1	752.98	10.97	0.0079	7.43
C–pTSA content	1756.81	1	1756.81	25.59	0.0005	11.34
A ²	1130.61	1	1130.61	16.47	0.0023	-8.86
B ²	634.35	1	634.35	9.24	0.0125	-6.63
C ²	593.81	1	593.81	8.65	0.0148	-6.42
AB	2.30	1	2.30	0.03	0.8584	-0.54
AC	27.28	1	27.28	0.40	0.5426	1.85
BC	1.92	1	1.92	0.03	0.8706	0.49
Residual	686.49	10	68.65			
Lack of fit	555.75	5	111.15	4.25	0.0691	
Pure error	130.74	5	26.15			
Total	8337.03	19				
Standard deviation. SD					8.2855	
R ²					0.9177	
Adj. R ²					0.8435	

^a degree of freedom.

^b for coded values

262

263 The ANOVA results of the model (Table 3) revealed that all the linear (A, B and C)
 264 and quadratic (A², B² and C²) model terms were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) on RS
 265 delignification by MW-assisted DES pretreatment. The coded values of the significant
 266 model terms indicated a positive effect of the linear terms (coded coefficient > 0) on

267 delignification, while the negative value of the quadratic terms could mean that increasing
268 these factors beyond a certain value could hinder delignification effectiveness. Low
269 efficiencies in extracting lignin from biomass can typically be attributed to two primary
270 factors: firstly, inadequate or not severe enough process conditions unable to efficiently
271 disrupt the lignocellulosic framework and extract lignin. Secondly, excessively severe
272 pretreatment conditions could promote the condensation and degradation of the extracted
273 lignin and hemicellulose, which in turn results in the deposition of substances known as
274 pseudolignin or humins on the surface of the pretreated solids, causing overestimation of
275 the lignin content (Abouelela et al., 2023). For instance, delignification effectiveness
276 exhibited a significant improvement when the temperature was raised from 50 °C (run 4,
277 15.7% delignification) to 80 °C (central point; 61.6% delignification), but declined when
278 further increasing the temperature to 110 °C (run 6; 53.2% delignification). Furthermore, it
279 was also observed a lignin-enrichment in the pretreated solids when increasing the
280 temperature from 80 °C (central points; 6.4% lignin content) to 110 °C (run 6, 9.2% lignin
281 content), thus confirming the redeposition of undesired substances on the pretreated solids
282 at the highest temperature.

283 Based on the second-order model developed, three-dimensional response surface
284 graphs and their corresponding contour plots were drawn to conduct a thorough study of
285 the effect of two variables, while maintaining the other constant at the central point. The
286 elliptical nature shown in Fig. 1 a-c confirmed that all the pretreatment variables studied
287 (temperature, time and pTSA content) have a strong effect on delignification. Indeed,
288 each 3D-surface plot clearly illustrates a threshold value for the different parameters,
289 beyond which delignification was not significantly improved or was even reduced. From
290 Fig. 1a, it could be seen that an initial increase of both temperature and pTSA content had

291 a notably positive effect on the delignification yield, which is in agreement with the
292 ANOVA results.

Fig. 1. Response surface plots of the interaction effect of two independent variables on the delignification after microwave-assisted DES pretreatment. The remaining factor was fixed at the center point: a) 22.5 min; b) pTSA 1.0 mole content; c) 80 °C.

293 The increase in the molar ratio of the acid HBD and the pretreatment temperature provide
294 more protons (H^+) for the cleavage of the lignin-carbohydrate complex and weaken DES
295 intermolecular strength. The released electron withdrawing groups can thus interact more
296 freely with lignin and the mass transfer could be enhanced, improving lignin solubilization

297 (Chen et al., 2020; Kohli et al., 2020). As shown in Fig. 1a, the use of temperatures as low
298 as 70 °C with a pTSA content higher than 1.0 would provide enough protons to disrupt the
299 lignocellulosic matrix. In fact, delignification effectiveness initially dropped at
300 temperatures over 100 °C with pTSA contents higher than 1.5, corroborating that the most
301 severe conditions tested in this study were not suitable for effective RS delignification. As
302 with temperature and pTSA content, initially extending the pretreatment time had a
303 positive effect on delignification until reaching a threshold value beyond which no further
304 improvement was found (Fig. 1b and 1c). Based on the analysis of Fig. 1b and 1c, a
305 pretreatment time of 20 minutes appears to be suitable for ensuring the efficient swelling of
306 the biomass in the DES for delignification.

307 All the response surfaces (Fig. 1) showed a wide operating range and indicated the
308 possibility of combining different pretreatment conditions to achieve effective lignin
309 extraction with delignification yields between 60-75%, which is in line with previous
310 studies using DES pretreatment for delignificate RS. For example, pretreatment of RS with
311 ChCl:LA (60 °C, 12 h, 5% w/w) leaded 60% delignification (Kumar et al., 2016), whereas
312 the use of ChCl:Gly (150 °C, 15 h, 5% w/w) yielded 52% delignification (Hossain et al.,
313 2021). Thus, ternary DES pretreatment under MW irradiation effectively reduces the
314 typically high severity levels required for efficiently extract lignin from RS in conventional
315 DES pretreatment and can thus be said to be a novel cost-effective alternative for biomass
316 delignification.

317 *3.3 Effect of MW-assisted DES pretreatment on RS crystallinity*

318 Changes in the crystallinity after MW-DES pretreatment were examined though
319 XRD. Samples from the center point (runs 2-3, 8-10, 16), the one with the highest
320 delignification (run 13), the sample without pTSA (run 17), and the raw RS were chosen
321 for analysis. As can be seen in Fig. S2, two characteristic peaks were present in the plotted

322 samples in the range of 18.5° and 22.1° representing the amorphous and crystalline regions.
323 The peak positions did not change significantly, indicating that the pretreated cellulose
324 retained its structure. The CrI of the untreated biomass was 52.3%, while the pretreated
325 samples exhibited a slightly higher CrI in the range 53.2-60.1%. Interestingly, in the
326 absence of pTSA (run 17), there was practically no change in the CrI (53.2%), as only
327 minimal removal of amorphous compounds (14.6% delignification, <90% xylan recovery)
328 was achieved. This corroborated the key role of acidity in the deconstruction of the
329 recalcitrant structure of biomass. By increasing the pTSA content, samples corresponding
330 to the central point exhibited a higher CrI of 58.7%, which was attributed to the greater
331 extraction of amorphous fractions (61.6% delignification, 60.8% xylan removal).
332 Meanwhile, the highest delignification and xylan removal achieved in run 13 (72.0%
333 delignification, 36.6% xylan recovery) led to the highest increase in the CrI (60.1%)
334 compared to the untreated material. These results confirmed the strong relationship
335 between crystallinity and the removal of amorphous compounds, as reported in previous
336 studies (Maibam and Goyal, 2022).

337 *3.4 Effect of MW-assisted DES pretreatment on RS saccharification: statistical analysis*

338 In order to assess the efficiency of the pretreatment in further converting the initial
339 polysaccharide content into monosaccharides, saccharification of untreated RS and after
340 MW-assisted DES pretreatment was evaluated. As can be seen in Table 4, raw RS
341 exhibited a low saccharification rate of only 17.7% and 11.7% for glucose and xylose,
342 respectively, thus confirming that polysaccharide conversion was severely hindered by the
343 recalcitrant biomass structure. Sugar saccharification was improved in all the cases
344 analyzed, ranging from 45.4-100% and 24.2-52.5% for glucose and xylose yield,
345 respectively. Notably, the highest delignification degree obtained in this study (72.0%
346 delignification, run 13) did not also provide the best polysaccharide conversion rates. In

347 this sense, it was found that beyond only 36.6% delignification (run 7), more than 90% of
 348 the initial glucan in the RS could be converted into glucose (92.4%), thus suggesting that
 349 there were other influential factors in the enhanced hydrolysis yield after MW-assisted
 350 pretreatment. These factors may include a larger surface area and pore volume, reduced
 351 polysaccharides polymerization degree as well as better allocation of the biomass
 352 compounds, which in overall enhanced the access of the enzymes to the polysaccharides
 353 (Zhao et al., 2012). Furthermore, the hydrolysis of xylose was reduced at the highest
 354 delignification rates, owing to the strong dependence between xylan and lignin extraction
 355 as mentioned in section 3.1.

356 **Table 4.** Enzymatic hydrolysis results for untreated and pretreated samples by MW-
 357 assisted DES pretreatment.

Run	Pretreatment conditions ^a			Enzymatic hydrolysis yield (%)	
	A	B	C	Glucose yield	Xylose yield
Raw RS				17.7	11.7
1	62.2	12.1	0.4	70.0	37.0
2 ^b	80.0	22.5	1.0	88.5	47.3
3 ^b	80.0	22.5	1.0	92.1	45.9
4	50.0	22.5	1.0	76.6	46.5
5	97.8	12.1	0.4	90.5	44.4
6	110.0	22.5	1.0	84.7	29.9
7	62.2	32.9	1.6	92.4	50.6
8 ^b	80.0	22.5	1.0	89.4	47.0
9 ^b	80.0	22.5	1.0	97.8	51.1
10 ^b	80.0	22.5	1.0	102.5	52.5
11	97.8	32.9	0.4	87.2	37.0
12	80.0	22.5	2.0	90.4	39.4
13	97.8	32.9	1.6	92.6	31.1
14	97.8	12.1	1.6	98.6	34.3
15	80.0	40.0	1.0	88.1	40.9
16 ^b	80.0	22.5	1.0	90.2	45.8
17	80.0	22.5	0.0	45.6	24.2
18	62.2	12.1	1.6	84.3	44.2
19	80.0	5.0	1.0	79.8	45.0
20	62.2	32.9	0.4	74.3	47.3

^a A: Temperature (°C); B: time (min); C: pTSA (mole content).

^b Central point of the experimental design.

358

359 Based on the results of Table 4, CCD was used for a further study on the effect of
 360 pretreatment temperature, time and pTSA mole content on the glucose and xylose yield
 361 after enzymatic hydrolysis. The second-order equations in terms of actual factors generated
 362 by CCD for glucose and xylose yield as response are the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Glucose yield (\%)} = & -63.87 + 2.05 \cdot \text{Temperature} + 1.80 \cdot \text{time} + 71.44 \cdot \text{pTSA} - \\ & 7.80\text{E}^{-3} \cdot \text{Temperature}^2 - 1.20 \text{E}^{-2} \cdot \text{time}^2 - 19.64 \text{pTSA}^2 - 1.46 \text{E}^{-2} \cdot \text{Temperature} \cdot \text{time} \quad (6) \\ & - 0.22 \cdot \text{Temperature} \cdot \text{pTSA} + 2.39\text{E}^{-2} \cdot \text{time} \cdot \text{pTSA} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Xylose yield (\%)} = & -67.20 + 1.87 \cdot \text{Temperature} + 1.91 \cdot \text{time} + 55.70 \cdot \text{pTSA} - \quad (7) \\ & 8.66 \text{E}^{-3} \cdot \text{Temperature}^2 - 1.00 \cdot \text{E}^{-2} \cdot \text{time}^2 - 14.21 \text{pTSA}^2 - 1.84 \text{E}^{-2} \cdot \text{Temperature} \cdot \text{time} \\ & - 0.31 \cdot \text{Temperature} \cdot \text{pTSA} + 6.63\text{E}^{-3} \cdot \text{time} \cdot \text{pTSA} \end{aligned}$$

363 The ANOVA results for each response (Table 5) showed that both models were
 364 highly significant at a 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$), while lack of fit was not significant
 365 in any case, indicating the goodness of the fitted models in predicting the responses. The
 366 good agreement between the experimental and predicted data by the models was confirmed
 367 by the values of the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.7587$ and 0.8216 for glucose and
 368 xylose yield, respectively). The ANOVA results given in Table 5 indicate the different
 369 influence of the studied variables for each response. For glucose yield, pTSA and pTSA²
 370 were found to be the two significant factors ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that system acidity was
 371 the main factor in hydrolyzing glucan into glucose after MW-assisted DES pretreatment. In
 372 the case of xylose yield, the ANOVA results indicate that temperature, temperature² and
 373 pTSA content² were the main factors affecting the hydrolysis of xylan into xylose ($p <$
 374 0.05 , Table 5), in agreement with the reported sensitivity of hemicellulose at high
 375 temperatures or in acidic environments.
 376

Table 5. ANOVA results of the CCD models for glucose and xylose yield as responses.

Source	Sum of squares	df ^a	Mean square	F-value	p-value	Coefficient ^b
Response: Glucose yield (%)						
Model	2218.19	9	246.47	3.49	0.0321	93.09
A–Temperature	276.39	1	276.39	3.92	0.0759	4.50
B–time	21.22	1	21.22	0.30	0.5954	1.25
C–pTSA content	1072.47	1	1072.47	15.20	0.0030	8.86
A ²	88.87	1	88.87	1.26	0.2879	-2.48
B ²	24.22	1	24.22	0.34	0.5709	-1.30
C ²	694.91	1	694.91	9.85	0.0105	-6.94
AB	58.78	1	58.78	0.83	0.3828	-2.71
AC	44.50	1	44.50	0.63	0.4455	-2.36
BC	0.18	1	0.18	0.00	0.9613	0.15
Residual	705.39	10	70.54			
Lack of fit	549.33	5	109.87	3.52	0.0967	
Pure error	156.05	5	31.21			
Total	2923.58	19				
Standard deviation, SD					8.3987	
R ²					0.7587	
Adj. R ²					0.5416	
Response: Xylose yield (%)						
Model	915.36	9	101.706	5.12	0.0088	48.13
A–Temperature	264.81	1	264.812	13.33	0.0045	-4.40
B–time	0.04	1	0.037	0.00	0.9665	-0.05
C–pTSA content	29.06	1	29.058	1.46	0.2544	1.46
A ²	109.50	1	109.498	5.51	0.0408	-2.76
B ²	16.92	1	16.919	0.85	0.3779	-1.08
C ²	363.64	1	363.637	18.30	0.0016	-5.02
AB	93.77	1	93.768	4.72	0.0550	-3.42
AC	87.72	1	87.717	4.41	0.0620	-3.31
BC	0.01	1	0.013	0.00	0.9798	0.04
Residual	198.73	10	19.873			
Lack of fit	158.31	5	31.662	3.92	0.0802	
Pure error	40.42	5	8.083			
Total	1114.08	19				
Standard deviation, SD					4.4579	
R ²					0.8216	
Adj. R ²					0.6611	

^adegree of freedom.^bfor coded values

378

379 The effect of the three pretreatment variables on the glucose and xylose yields were

380 represented by the 3D response surface plots (Fig. 2 a-f).

Fig. 2. Response surface plots of the interaction effect of two independent variables on the glucose yield (a-c) and xylose yield (d-f) after microwave-assisted DES pretreatment. The remaining factor was fixed at the center point: a,d) 22.5 min; b,e) pTSA 1.0; c,f) 80 °C.

382 In the case of glucose yield, the response surfaces (Fig. 2a-c) indicated a favorable
383 effect on the initial increase of temperature and pTSA content, while it can be seen that the
384 severest temperature and pTSA conditions did not improve the glucose yield. In this sense,
385 the effect of deposition of condensed lignin and humins detected when using 110 °C (run
386 6) could be one of the reasons ascribed to the decline in the glucose yield for the severest
387 conditions, as well as the possible degradation of cellulose when using such harsh
388 pretreatment variables. The effect of time seems to be negligible as observed by the
389 linearity of the time plane in Fig. 2 b-c, which agrees with the ANOVA results, as time was
390 not found to be significant in glucose yield. Particularly, the low effect of pretreatment
391 time in glucose yield can be seen in Fig. 2c, which clearly shows that using a pTSA
392 content above 0.5 for 80 °C can achieve a similar glucose yield of more than 80%,
393 regardless of the time used. From the three glucose yield response surfaces (Fig. 2 a-c) it
394 could be concluded that there was a widespread chance to combine different pretreatment
395 conditions which lead to glucose yields of over 90%.

396 Regarding the effect of the pretreatment variables on xylose yield as response, the
397 3D-response surfaces (Fig. 2 d-f) indicated a linear effect of pretreatment time, while
398 pTSA and temperature exhibited a curved response, thereby corroborating the stronger
399 influence of these parameters over time, as suggested by the ANOVA results. The graphs
400 also show that both the mild and extreme pretreatment conditions provided the lowest
401 xylose yields as ineffective deconstruction impedes hydrolysis, while increasing the
402 severity was found to be highly sensitive to xylan preservation in the pretreated solids. In
403 contrast to glucose yield, the operating range which provided the highest xylose yields (>
404 45%) was more restricted. Meanwhile, pretreatment time was not found to have a
405 significant influence and practically the same xylose yields could be obtained from all the
406 time spectra tested for a given temperature and pTSA content, as can be seen in Fig. 2 e-f.

407 In short, the ANOVA results and response surface graphs demonstrated the
408 different effect of pretreatment conditions in the glucose and xylose yield after enzymatic
409 hydrolysis. Therefore, selection of the pretreatment conditions should balance efficient
410 conversion of both polysaccharides while keeping energy requirements as low as possible,
411 which improve the overall feasibility of the valorization process of RS by MW-assisted
412 DES pretreatment.

413 *3.5 Selection of pretreatment conditions*

414 In this study, it was claimed that the use of MW-assisted DES pretreatment could
415 efficiently extract lignin from RS as well as provide efficient polysaccharide conversion.
416 Even though the ANOVA results suggested that different pretreatment conditions could be
417 optimized for each response, it is possible to establish a compromise between obtaining
418 both efficient delignification and improved saccharification of polysaccharides. Neither
419 high delignification rates nor severe pretreatment conditions were required for effective
420 sugar hydrolysis and could even be detrimental, especially to the hemicellulose fraction.
421 Based on the above results, selecting the pretreatment conditions at the central point in the
422 CCD (80 °C, 22.5 min and 1.0 pTSA mole content) seems to be the best way to obtain both
423 efficient delignification (61.6 ± 5.1) and good glucose (93.4 ± 5.6) and xylose hydrolysis
424 (48.3 ± 2.5). Overall, these conditions released a total of 78.3% of the initial
425 polysaccharides in the untreated RS in the form of monosaccharides. The selection of the
426 pretreatment conditions was also carried out by considering energetical and solvent issues
427 and neither parameter was chosen at a high level, thus providing pretreatment conditions
428 with a relatively low pretreatment temperature, time and acidity at the same time.
429 In the search of a cost-effective pretreatment approach, the cyclic use of the DES also
430 plays a crucial role for developing sustainable fractionation strategies within the current
431 biorefineries. Herein, the recovery and reuse of the ternary DES was assessed by

432 investigating the delignification and saccharification efficiency for two recycles under the
433 selected pretreatment conditions (80 °C, 22.5 min, ChCl:pTSA:EG 1:1:9). The ternary DES
434 was recycled for two times, obtaining an average of DES recovery of 85% w/w. As can be
435 seen in Fig. S3, the delignification degree decreased from 61.6% (fresh run) to 37.5%
436 (second reuse). This reduced fractionation efficiency could be related to the accumulation
437 of impurities in the DES as well as a reduction in its hydrogen bonding interaction ability
438 (Wang et al., 2020). For the recycling experiments, the glucose saccharification yield was
439 93.4%, 83.3% and 81.0% for the first, second and third use, respectively, whereas xylose
440 yields achieved were 48.3%, 42.4% and 39.0%, respectively. These results indicated an
441 initial drop in saccharification efficiency with the recycled DES, followed by a subsequent
442 stabilization, resulting in nearly identical saccharification patterns for the two reuses of the
443 DES. Despite the slight decrease in the hydrolysis of sugars in the reuses, the
444 saccharification effectiveness remained significantly higher compared to untreated RS,
445 showcasing approximately a 4.5 and 3.3-fold increase in glucose and xylose yield,
446 respectively. Based on the above results, it was claimed that the ternary DES still had value
447 for reuse, which can improve the feasibility and economic benefits of the developed
448 pretreatment.

449 To check the joint effectiveness of ternary DES and the use of MW, the effect of
450 the heating mode was also compared for the selected pretreatment conditions (80 °C, 22.5
451 min) as well as doubling the pretreatment time (45 min) (Fig. 3). In terms of
452 delignification, MW-assisted pretreatment exhibited superior performance (61.6%)
453 compared to conductive heating (CH) (40.4%), also even with the doubling of pretreatment
454 time in CH (53.1% delignification), thus confirming the enhanced deconstruction
455 effectiveness through the introduction of MW heating. The most likely mechanism
456 underlying RS pretreatment with ternary DES involves a synergistic effect between HBA

Fig. 3. Comparison between the heating modes (microwave, MW or conductive heating, CH) in terms of pretreatment effectiveness and energetic consumption.

457 and both HBD. Specifically, ChCl plays an important role in lignin extraction by forming
 458 hydrogen bonds between its halogen ions (Cl⁻) and hydroxyl groups in lignin (Wang and
 459 Lee, 2021). The addition of pTSA increases the proton/active acidic sites of DES, aiding
 460 the cleavage of lignin hydrogen and ether bonds while partially solubilizing hemicellulose.
 461 As a hydrotrope, pTSA hydrophobic fractions (toluene moiety of pTSA) can surround
 462 hydrophobic molecules such as lignin, assisting in its solubilization (Song et al., 2019).
 463 Meanwhile, the incorporation of the EG can enhance lignin extraction by providing free
 464 hydroxyl groups that interact with the etherified hydroxyl groups in lignin (Zhang et al.,
 465 2016). Additionally, the introduction of MW not only promotes direct and more efficient
 466 heating but also enhances the ionic and dielectric properties of the DES. This improvement
 467 favors interactions between the ternary DES and RS, resulting in enhanced RS
 468 deconstruction. Indeed, a previous study demonstrated that DES containing pTSA showed
 469 higher dielectric properties than other DES, making them ideal choices for use under
 470 microwaves due to their faster heating rate (Mao et al., 2023). As a result of the improved
 471 biomass disruption and delignification, MW-assisted technology resulted in a higher

472 saccharification rate both in terms of glucose (93.4%) and xylose yield (48.3) compared to
473 both cases of CH (80.9-87.2% glucose yield; 33.9-25.8% xylose yield), thus corroborating
474 the joint contribution of MW and ternary DES for improving the polysaccharide
475 conversion from RS.

476 Energy consumption for each pretreatment was assessed by considering the power
477 and time of each pretreatment. At the studied temperature (80 °C), MW consumed a
478 maximum potency of 260 W for 22.5 min, whereas in the case of CH a power to
479 temperature ratio of 9.2 was used. As shown in Fig. 3, MW-assisted technology resulted in
480 significantly lower energy consumption (17.4 kJ/g biomass) compared to conductive
481 heating under the same operational conditions (61.6 kJ/g biomass). Moreover, the use of
482 CH for 45 min implied an exacerbated energy consumption (123.3 kJ/g biomass) compared
483 to MW-assisted technology, as well as a lower efficiency performance. Overall, MW
484 irradiation not only provided better pretreatment performance than CH but also resulted in
485 a lower energy consumption technology, rendering a dual advantage of improved
486 efficiency and operational cost within the biorefinery framework.

487 As a potential available lignocellulosic feedstock, the pretreatment of RS has also
488 been investigated through MW-assisted technologies as well as DES pretreatment (Table
489 6). Several authors reported the application of MW-assisted technologies in the
490 pretreatment of RS using hydrothermolysis (Valles et al., 2020), IL ([Bmim][Cl]) (Sorn et
491 al., 2019) or binary DES (ChCl:FA 1:2) (Sawhney et al., 2023) at extremely high
492 temperatures (>145 °C), obtaining low saccharification efficiencies (35.8-72.6 % glucose
493 yield, < 33.2% xylose yield), compared to that reported in this work. Furthermore, DES
494 pretreatment of RS by conventional heating could yield excellent delignification efficiency
495 (> 75%), although requiring severe pretreatment conditions (>120 °C, > 1 h). Nevertheless,
496 DES pretreatment of RS did not provide good further conversions into monosaccharides,

497 especially in the case of hemicellulose (< 20% xylose yield) (Hou et al., 2018; Li et al.,
 498 2018a; Maibam and Goyal, 2022). Moreover, it should be noted that pretreatment with
 499 recycled DES still provide superior saccharification patterns than those reported in
 500 literature, corroborating the great recyclability of the ternary DES.

501 **Table 6.** Comparison of different pretreatments of RS using MW-assisted technologies and
 502 DES.

Type	Pretreatment conditions	Enzymatic hydrolysis			Reference
		Delignification (%)	Enzyme dosage (FPU/g biomass)	Glucose and xylose yield (%)	
MW-assisted hydrothermolysis	100-200 °C 40 min 10% w/w	13.3	13.5	35.8 glucose yield 33.2% xylose yield	(Valles et al., 2020)
MW -assisted ionic liquid ([Bmim][Cl])	150 °C, 5 min, 5% w/w	57.0	50	61.1% glucose yield 19.1% xylose yield	(Sorn et al., 2019)
MW-assisted DES (ChCl:FA 1:2) + laccase	145 °C, 8.8 min, 5.5% w/w	-	N.I	72.6% glucose yield -	(Sawhney et al., 2023)
DES (ChCl:Acetic Acid 1:3.59)	126 °C, 149.6 min, 7.5% w/w	83.1	35	92.2 ^b % glucose yield	(Maibam and Goyal, 2022)
DES (ChCl:OA 1:1)	120 °C, 60 min, 5% w/w	75	40 ^a	52.9% glucose yield 0.4% xylose yield	(Hou et al., 2018)
DES (ChCl:LA 1:5)	120 °C, 180 min, 5% w/w	75.5	N.I	65.8% glucose yield 19.1% xylose yield	(Li et al., 2018)
MW-assisted DES (ChCl:pTSA:EG 1:1:9)	80 °C, 22.5 min, 10% w/w	61.6	30	93.4% glucose yield 48.3% xylose yield	This study

^aFPU/g cellulose

^breferred to pretreated RS.

N.I: not indicated

503 The results reported in this study showed the potential of ternary DES under MW
504 irradiation in pretreating biomass with better sugar conversions than previous studies while
505 reducing the severity of the process. The proposed MW-assisted ternary DES pretreatment
506 (80 °C, 22.5 min, ChCl:pTSA:EG 1:1:9) thus has significant advantages and can be
507 considered an efficient novel pathway for the valorization of RS polysaccharides, which
508 could provide a new thought for improve the profitability and economic benefits of the
509 biorefinery. Considering its low energy consumption, the good recyclability of the ternary
510 DES along the efficient saccharification of RS, this pretreatment technology holds great
511 potential for the development of its large-scale use guided to assess its future
512 commercialization.

513 **4. Conclusions**

514 This study disclosed the potential of MW-assisted ternary DES pretreatment as a
515 novel technology for RS fractionation and enzymatical conversion, showing that excessive
516 lignin extractions and severe pretreatment conditions were not necessary and could even be
517 prejudicial. Analyzing the results by the response surface method, it was possible to select
518 a mild operating temperature (80 °C), a short time (22.5 min) and a low acidic HBD molar
519 ratio (ChCl:pTSA:EG 1:1:9) to simultaneously provide a high delignification rate (61.4%),
520 as well as an excellent glucose yield (93.4%) and a good xylose yield (48.3%). The
521 selected pretreatment conditions under MW provided an enhanced effectiveness both in
522 terms of effectiveness and energy consumption compared to conductive heating. Moreover,
523 the ternary DES showed a good recyclability pattern, improving the economic benefits of
524 the process. The proposed MW-assisted ternary DES pretreatment could represent a novel,
525 energy-saving and cost-effective approach for the deconstruction of lignocellulosic
526 biomass for its further conversion to a broad range of value-added products, holding great
527 potential to be recognized as a significant technology in the biorefinery context.

528 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

529 **Helena Poy:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation,
530 Methodology, Writing – original draft, Validation. **Estela Lladosa:** Conceptualization,
531 Data curation, Formal analysis, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Validation
532 **Adrián Arcís:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Carmen Gabaldón:** Conceptualization,
533 Data curation, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Resources,
534 Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Sonia Loras:** Data curation, Formal analysis,
535 Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Validation.

536 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

537 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
538 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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545 **Appendix A. Supplementary data**

546 Supplementary material related to this article can be found in the online version.

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Supplementary Information

Microwave-assisted ternary deep eutectic solvent pretreatment for improved rice straw saccharification under mild pretreatment conditions

Helena Poy, Estela Lladosa*, Adrián Arcís, Carmen Gabaldón, Sonia Loras

Department of Chemical Engineering, Universitat de València, Av. De la Universitat S/N,
46100, Burjassot, Spain.

*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: estela.lladosa@uv.es (E. Lladosa)

Fig. S1. Linear relationship between xylan recovery and delignification obtained after MW-assisted DES pretreatment of RS.

Fig. S2. XRD patterns of raw RS and pretreated samples with MW-assisted DES.

Fig. S3. Effect of ternary DES recycling on the delignification and sugar saccharification after MW-assisted pretreatment.

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